

Maximizing Number of Reactions versus Number of Particles with Energy e_i in Statistical Mechanics

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Traditionally, it seems statistical mechanical counting (and maximization) schemes using factorials are based on counting the number of systems in an ensemble with energy E_i or the number of particles in a system (e.g. a gas) with energy e_i . In this note, we try to argue that the counting (and maximization) may be that of the number of “generalized” reactions involving a particle with e_i , rather than the number of particles with e_i . For Maxwell-Boltzmann statistics, the probability for e_i to react is $f(e_i)$ (i.e. for e_1 to scatter with e_2 , the probability is $f(e_1)f(e_2)$). Thus, the number of particles and the number of reactions involving a particle with e_i are proportional. For the Fermi Dirac and Bose Einstein cases, however, this already changes. For more general cases, it seems clearer that it is the number of reactions which is related to the entropy and not configurations.

Traditional Statistical Mechanics

Factorials are often used in statistical mechanics. For example:

$M! / (m_1! m_2! \dots)$ is used to count the number of arrangements of systems in an ensemble.

The total number of systems is M and the total energy MU . m_i represents the number of systems with energy E_i . From this, one may derive the form of the canonical partition function (1), by finding the m_i which maximize the above.

Furthermore, in statistical mechanics texts (1):

$\prod_i g_i^{n_i} / n_i!$ where g_i is a “degeneracy” is used to calculate the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution

$g! / [n! (g-n)!]$ (g =degeneracy) is used to calculate the Fermi-Dirac distribution and

$\prod_i (n_i + g_i - 1)! / [n_i! (g_i - 1)!]$ is used to calculate the Bose-Einstein distribution

In all of these cases, one counts various arrangements of the “number of particles n_i ” with energy e_i . In all cases as well, $\exp(-(e_i - u)/T)$ is an important component of $f(e_i)$, the probability or the number of particles with e_i .

In this note, we argue it seems one is really counting the number of “generalized” reactions in which a particle with e_i is involved. Thus, it seems it is the activity which is important in counting (i.e. factorial schemes) and maximization. The number of particles with energy e_i i.e. $f(e_i)$ is involved, but is not the “entity” which appears in counting schemes. This may then be

generalized to entropy which is also involved in the “number of reactions” of particles with energy e_i .

Scattering

In previous notes, we have argued that time reversal elastic scattering balance may be used to determine the MB, FD and BE distributions as well as more general cases. A key idea is that single particles possess an energy e_i which may change through interactions with other particles such that energy is conserved. Thus, interactions change the energy of a particle in a way that no energy is wasted. One need not necessarily consider only two body scattering. A second key idea we use is that the reaction may be written in terms of “independent” quantities. The MB case is the simplest where the independent quantity is $f(e_i)$. This represents the number of particles with energy e_i as well as the probability for a particle with energy e_i to scatter. For example for: $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$, one has:

$$f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4) \quad ((1))$$

Because $f(e_i)$ represents the number of particles with energy e_i , it seems statistical mechanics is developed from the point of view of counting the distribution of energy among particles. We argue it is the counting of reactions of a particle with energy e_i which is important.

Next, consider FD and BE scattering. Here there is a repression factor for FD and an enhancement factor for BE (e.g. a fermion cannot scatter into an occupied state and a boson has an probability enhanced by $n+1$ for scattering into a state with n bosons). Then ((1)) changes to:

$$f(e_1) [1 -/+ f(e_3)] f(e_2) [1 -/+ f(e_4)] = f(e_3) [1 -/+ f(e_1)] f(e_4) [1 -/+ f(e_2)] \quad ((2)) - \text{for fermions } + \text{ for bosons}$$

Thus, one may consider $f(e_i) / [1 -/+ f(e_i)]$ as a new generalized object related to independent reactions. It is $f(e_i) / [1 -/+ f(e_i)]$ which equals $\exp(-1/T(e_i - u))$ ($u = \text{chemical potential}$). $\exp(-1/T(e_i - u))$, however, is the solution of “maximizing” the counting scheme of systems in an ensemble in statistical mechanics texts. The factor $\exp(-1/T(e_i - u))$ may also be obtained by taking \ln of ((2)) and equating it to conservation of energy $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$.

General Case

One may write a more general two body “independent” scattering factor as:

$g_1(f(e_i)) / g_2(f(e_i)) \quad ((3))$ Here $g_1(f(e_i))$ is the probability to react and $g_2(f(e_i))$ an enhancement or hindrance, such as in the fermion or boson case. Because of independence in two body scattering, one has:

Product over i $g_1(f(e_i))/g_2(f(e_i))$ Taking the \ln and equating to $-(e_i-u)/T$ yields an equation which may be solved for $f(e_i)$ i.e.

$$(g_1(f(e_i))/g_2(f(e_i))) = \exp(-(e_i-u)/T) \quad ((4))$$

$\exp(-(e_i-u)/T)$, however, is the usual MB factor, but it applies to a new entity which is the generalized probability for a particle with e_i to be involved in a reaction. The term “generalized” is used because there may be a reaction probability g_1 together with a restriction or enhancement, such as in the case of fermions or bosons. Thus, the analysis of a system in equilibrium seems to be related to the counting and maximization of reactions (not particles) related to an energy of e_i .

We suggest one may use:

$M! / (m_1! m_2! \dots)$ ((5a)) where m_i represents the number of reactions in which a particle with energy e_i is involved.

Usually in statistical mechanics, m_i represents the number of particles with e_i subject to the two constraints $\sum_i m_i = M$ and $\sum_i m_i e_i = MU$, ((5b)) where U is the average energy.

In (1), ((5a)) is generalized to a complex generating function which is solved by finding saddle points and performing contour integration. The final result is an “equilibrium” value for m_i equal to $\exp(-E_i/T)$. The two constraints ((5b)) do not seem to be used in the calculation, although the parameter U appears. The idea seems to be to develop a method which bypasses the constraints, although at the saddle point, U , a parameter in the calculation, satisfies:

$$U = [\sum_i E_i \exp(-E_i/T)] / [\sum_i \exp(-E_i/T)] \quad (\text{This may be mapped back to the constraint})$$

T is another parameter in the calculation. Thus, it seems one does not have to use an a priori constraint $\sum_i m_i e_i = MU$. It arises out of the calculation if one carries a parameter U . If such is the case, the above analysis should also apply to the maximization of “reactions” as opposed to arrangements of ensembles. Thus, having $\exp(-(e_i-u)/T)$ be proportional to the number of generalized reactions, maximizes the “activity” in the system and creates equilibrium.

These ideas should carry over to entropy i.e. entropy should be a measure of the activity in a system, if the above holds. If one uses Kaniadakis (2) entropy then:

$$S = \int d\text{phase space} \int df \ln[g_1(f(e))/g_2(f(e))] \quad ((6))$$

This entropy is obtained from ((4)) i.e. $\ln[g_1(f(e))/g_2(f(e))] ((7)) = -(e_i-u)/T$ which follows from a scattering balance. One desires an entropy density S_d such that d/df of S_d with the Lagrange

multiplier $-(e_i - u)/T$ yields ((6)). Thus, one integrates ((7)) so that d/df returns the function. One may see explicitly that the Kaniadakis entropy involves scattering considerations.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it seems statistical mechanics texts consider maximizing counting schemes using factorials in order to analyze arrangements or configurations of systems or particles where $n_i =$ the number of systems or particles with energy e_i . Entropy then becomes a measure of this arrangement. In this note, we argue that the maximization of reactions or activity is the important factor. Thus, the canonical factor $\exp(-E/T)$ which may be generalized to $\exp(-(e_i - u)/T)$, we argue, applies to a maximization of reactions. This carries over into the Kaniadakis entropy which also seems to be a measure of reactions or activity in a system.

References

1. Huang, Kerson. Statistical Mechanics (Wiley, 1987) (page 182, page 198)
2. Kaniadakis, G. NonLinear Kinematics Underlying Generalized Statistics (2018)
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/cond-mat/0103467.pdf>